

OSCAR Survey Instruments

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Table of Contents

Project summary and main objectives	3
About the Project	3
Project partners	3
Pre Workshop Survey	4
Post Workshop Survey	5

Project summary and main objectives

About the Project

Project title: OSCAR, the “Online, open learning recommendations and mentoring towards Sustainable research CAREers”

Funding: Erasmus+ Key Action 204 Higher Education

Duration: September 2020-August 2023

Budget: 427 818 €

The principal objective of OSCAR E+ Strategic Partnership was to develop, deploy and validate a personalised AI based learning, training and online mentoring service for researchers in order to support researchers, research master students and doctoral training participants in their career management and mental health awareness skills development. Therefore, the OSCAR project focused on the development of an online, AI driven open learning recommendation framework focusing on mental health and career management.

Project partners

Coordinator

TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University Library, Germany

Partners

USI - University of Siegen, Germany

CALP – Career & Life Planning, Ireland

RUMO, Portugal

Marie Curie Alumni Association, Belgium

SciLink Foundation, Netherlands

Associated Partner

Eurodoc – The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, Belgium

Pre Workshop Survey

1. I consent to my data being used for research purposes within the OSCAR project
2. What is your nationality? (You can type multiple if that applies)
3. What is your age?
4. To which gender do you most identify with? (Male, Non-binary / third gender, Female)
5. Do you have any caring responsibilities? (No, Children, Elderly/Parents, Others)
6. What is your area of study? (Eg. Engineering, Healthcare, Economics...)
7. What is your job title?
8. Do you identify with any minority groups which may have influenced career options and opportunities?
9. If so, enter what group you identify with (*optional)
10. Do you work as an international mobile researcher? (That is, working as a researcher outside of the country you normally reside in)
11. How many years have you been working as a researcher?
12. How many of these years were paid?

How satisfied are you with your general life situation with respect to the following dimensions? (Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree)

13. Career Trajectory
14. Work Environment
15. Family Life
16. Social Life

Post Workshop Survey

1. I consent to my data being collected for research purposes.
2. I participated in the workshop as a (Mentor, Participant)
3. Which of the following topics were of most interest to you? (Rank using the numbers on the right - 1 being of most interest) - (Stress Management, Finding a Work Life Balance, Goal Setting, Career Planning)

Using the sliders below, indicate how much you agree with the following statements:

4. I found it easy to register for the workshops
5. The registration information provided was clear and informative
6. The topics presented were relevant to my situation
7. Overall, the workshops improved my understanding of mental health
8. Overall, the workshops improved my understanding of career planning
9. I would recommend these workshops to others
10. Is there anything we could improve for organising future workshop days?

We want to understand your experience with the eDoer application. Using the sliders, indicate how much you agree with the following statements. -

11. I found the application easy to navigate
12. I found the application instructions clear and easily understood
13. The learning topics selected covered my needs
14. The learning modules provided helpful information
15. I would recommend the eDoer application to others
16. Did eDoer provide you content that aligned with your learning needs?
17. Was there any issues or bugs that you came across when using the application?
18. Do you have any recommendations on how we can improve the eDoer application?
19. Did you participate in the afternoon mentoring sessions?
20. My mentor was: (*Select Mentor*)

With respects to your mentoring session, how much do you agree with the following statements: (Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree)

21. The sessions fostered positive conversations
 22. The amount of communication with our mentor was sufficient
 23. The amount of communication between participants was helpful
 24. I developed a sense of connection with my mentor
 25. I developed a sense of connection with my session peers
 26. The process was sensitive to my situation and gave me a sense of confidentiality
 27. Overall, were you happy with the mentoring sessions and the support they provided?
- Any suggestions for improvement will be passed onto mentors anonymously.